

Advanced optimal GA-PID controller for BLDC motor

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ABSTRACT

The brushless direct current (BLDC) motor is characterized by high torque, which made it widely used in many industrial applications. To improve the working performance of the BLDC motor, the addition of controllers such as proportional integral derivative (PID) is adopted. To obtain high-performance controllers, the design process is adopted to develop a suitable algorithm. The genetic algorithm (GA) was chosen to tune the PID controller and get suitable parameters for each of k_p , k_i and k_d with self-tuning. The design process is based on BLDC motor control using the GA to tune the traditional PID controller. Simulations were carried out for three cases including the absence of controllers secondly, by using the traditional control unit and finally with the GA. The integral time absolute error (ITAE) type error control standard for BLDC motor control system was selected. After conducting the simulation, the results demonstrated the superiority of the GA over the traditional ones in terms of response speed, (stability, rise, and settling) time and percentage overshoots details will be mentioned the model in the subsequent paragraphs of the research, finally the simulation results indicate the development and improvement of BLDC motor operation and performance during real time.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Brushless direct current (BLDC) motors are a type of DC motor in which the windings in the rotor are replaced by permanent magnets to provide the required clearance throughput, while the windings are in the stator to produce the magnetic field. The magnetic field produced by the stator and rotor will rotate at the same frequency. BLDC motor is an electric motor that drives electric vehicles and electric cars. BLDC motors have wide industrial uses such as servo applications and applications that require stable operation and precise speed control in industrial processes. The use of BLDC motor in industrial applications has huge advantages in saving costs and time compared to dc motor [1]–[4]. BLDC motors are preferred as small motors in horsepower control because of the outstanding performance characteristics of high efficiency, high torque, silent operation, reliability, compact shape, low maintenance, small size compared to brushed DC motors [5]–[8] BLDC motors must be appropriately designed to have good magnetic coupling in order to be used in applications cutting, lifting and bracing [9]–[11]. BLDC motor permanent magnet type its rotor and electromagnetic stator was used and its speed was controlled by a microcontroller and a the inverter was simulated using the MATLAB software [6], [12]–[14].

The some of past studies included controlling the direct torque control (DTC) and monitoring the flow of the BLDC motor of the centrifugal actuator, and the researchers used a program MATLAB/Simulink

and to simulate the system. The speed of the DC motor was controlled using proportional integral derivative (PID) controller and the MATLAB simulation program in cases of no load, gradual change of loads and sudden load. Also include MATLAB/Simulink program for BLDC motor speed control using neural networks with closed loop control for and testing the efficiency and sensitivity of this controller. The researchers introduced the MATLAB/Simulink program to control the speed of BLDC motor using the controller type PID and conducted tests to verify the use of the controller to control is appropriate and efficient. The parameters of PID were tuned by using genetic algorithm (GA) and design synchronous controller which depends on the speed and phase difference of the motor, which achieves the effect of control that the dual device-driven mechanical vibration system in terms of motor speed and phase difference in stable condition. PID is the most widely used control algorithm in industrial applications for several decades due to its good robustness, simple, good performance that ensures automated control systems [15]–[19]. The PID control algorithm is described by 3-parameters proportional (P), integral (I), derivative (D), where P depends upon the present error, I depends upon the cumulating of past error, D depends upon the retelling of future error based on current rate of change in error. Currently there are several methods developed for the synthesis of model control algorithms are widely used to optimize the problem of PID controller [20]–[22]. GA have been successfully used to solve complex optimization problems to provide practical solutions in calculating different parameters for the control unit due to their high accuracy and fast convergence [23]–[25].

GA are based on the essential (natural selection and natural inheritance). Natural selection means that organisms continue to survive those that have adapted to environmental conditions, and organisms that have been eliminated are those that have not natural inheritance is breeding of individuals chosen to produce new ones through intermarriage. In GA to solve the problems, the number of individuals that make up the first population is completely randomly determined and the following stages can be grouped into two stages: genetic operations (crossover and mutation) and evolutionary process (selection). GA that starts to solve problems are set of points, by encoding these points first. Each structure makes a solution set (population) called a chromosome (individual). Chromosomes are made up chains of symbols called Genes [26]–[29]. This paper presents simulation models by using MATLAB to improve operation and performance of BLDC motor by using PID controller and GA-PID controller and comparison without controller in order to obtain best results.

2. FUNCTION AND MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF BLDC MOTOR

The BLDC motor is different from the traditional DC motor in that it has three phases, its dynamic features is like to permanent magnet DC motor. Figure 1 shows transfer function of BLDC motor [30], [31]. The mathematical equations of BLDC motor are:

$$V_{app}(t) = L \frac{di(t)}{dt} + R \cdot i(t) + V_{emf}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$V_{emf}(t) = K_b \cdot \omega(t) \quad (2)$$

$$T(t) = K_t \cdot i(t) \quad (3)$$

$$T(t) = J \frac{d\omega(t)}{dt} + D \cdot \omega(t) \quad (4)$$

The transfer function of BLDC motor can be shown in (5):

$$\frac{\omega(s)}{V_{app}(s)} = \frac{K_t}{LJS^2(LD+RJ)S+K_tK_b} \quad (5)$$

Where R is stator resistance, L is inductance of the stator, K_t is motor torque constant, K_b is back electromotive force constant, J is moment of inertia and D is viscous coefficient.

Figure 1. Transfer function of BLDC motor system

3. SIMULATION MODELS OF BLDC MOTOR

This section shows the simulation model of BLDC motor include input and output system and transfer function of BLDC motor. Table 1 shows the parameters of BLDC motor proposes in this paper. Figure 2 shows simulation model of BLDC without controller, while Figure 3 illustrates the simulation model by using traditional controller PID which using to improve performance of BLDC motor. Figure 4 shows two simulation model of BLDC motor without and with PID controller. Figure 5 indicates to the simulation model by using optimum system GA-PIC to obtain essential modification by select best values for control parameters of PID controller to optimize system. Figure 6 shows the flow chart of GA.

Table 1. Parameters of BLDC motor

Number	Parameters	Symbols	Amounts
1	Stator resistance	R	21.2 Ohm
2	Inductance of the stator	L	0.052 H
3	Motor torque constant	Kt	0.1433 Kg.m/A
4	Back electromotive force constant	Kb	0.149 V/rad/S
5	Moment of inertia	J	1×10-5 k.gm S ² /rad
6	Viscous coefficient	D	1×10-4 kg.m S/rad

Figure 2. Simulation model of BLDC motor without controller

Figure 3. Simulation model of BLDC motor with tuning PID controller

Figure 4. Simulation model of BLDC motor without and with PID controller

Figure 5. Simulation model of BLDC motor with GA-PID controller

Figure 6. The flowchart of genetic algorithm

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, there are three parts, first part simulation results without controller that show in subsection 4.1. Second part simulation results with PID controller that show in subsection 4.2. Third part simulation results with GA-PID controller that show in subsection 4.3.

4.1. Simulation results without controller

This section discuss the simulation results obtain by using MATLAB/Simulink program. Figure 7(a) shows the response of the system without controller at time 0.02 sec and Figure 7(b) at time 0.2 sec represented in speed of motor. From this figure, the percentage over shoot=20%, rise time=0.003 sec where as settling time=0.018 sec.

Figure 7. Simulation response of BLDC motor without controller (a) at 0.02 sec and (b) at 0.2 sec

4.2. Simulation results with PID controller

This section discusses the response of the system by using a PID controller to improve the operation and performance of the BLDC motor. Figure 8 shows the response of the system, indicating a reduction in overshoot to 7.1%, a rise time of 0.0279 sec, and a settling time of 0.102 sec. Therefore, the system reaches a steady state in less time than the first case without a controller. The values of the parameters for the PID controller are $K_p=0.062988$, $K_d=4.7342e-05$, and $K_i=3.242$. Figure 9 shows the controller parameters of the PID controller and (performance and robustness). Figure 10 illustrates the response of the system for each simulation model of BLDC without and with a PID controller. These results refer to obtaining a good response by using a PID controller compared to without a controller.

4.3. Simulation results with GA-PID controller

This section deals with the use of genetic-PID optimization for improving the response of the BLDC motor and obtaining the best results in order to develop and improve the performance and operation of the motor by improving the parameters of the PID controller to reach optimization. Figure 11 shows the response of the system by using GA-PID optimization. This figure indicates that the overshoot decreases to 0, and each of the settling time and rise time are 0.65×10^{-7} sec and 0.22×10^{-7} sec, respectively, and the system reaches the steady state in a much shorter time than the previous two states (without a controller and with a controlling PID controller). The values of the control parameters are $K_p=0.183$, $K_d=4.996$, $K_i=0.001$ at iteration=127. Figure 12 indicates the optimization tools for GA-PID. Figures 13-15 show the GA, fitness value, average distance between individuals, respectively.

Figure 8. Simulation response of BLDC with PID controller

Controller Parameters		
	Tuned	Block
P	0.062988	1
I	3.2421	1
D	4.7342e-05	0
N	6131.777	100
Performance and Robustness		
	Tuned	Block
Rise time	0.0279 seconds	0.0028 seconds
Settling time	0.102 seconds	NaN seconds
Overshoot	7.1 %	22.5 %
Peak	1.07	1.22
Gain margin	Inf dB @ Inf rad/s	Inf dB @ Inf rad/s
Phase margin	69 deg @ 53.7 rad/s	43 deg @ 461 rad/s
Closed-loop stability	Stable	Stable

Figure 9. Controller parameters of PID controller & performance and robustness

Figure 10. Simulation response of BLDC without and with PID controller

Figure 11. Response of system by using GA-PID optimization

Optimization Tool

File Help

Problem Setup and Results

Solver: ga - Genetic Algorithm

Problem

Fitness function:

Number of variables:

Constraints:

Linear inequalities: A: b:

Linear equalities: Aeq: beq:

Bounds: Lower: Upper:

Nonlinear constraint function:

Integer variable indices:

Run solver and view results

Use random states from previous run

Current iteration:

Changes applied.
 Stop requested.
 Objective function value: 7.53849574536178E-5
 Optimization terminated: Stop requested

Final point:

1	2	3
	0.183	4.996
		0.001

Figure 12. The optimization tools for GA-PID controller

Figure 13. Simulation response for genetic algorithm

Figure 14. Fitness value

Figure 15. Average distance between individual

Table 2 shows the values of control parameters (KP, Kd and Ki) for PID controller and GA-PID optimization while Table 3 shows the values of simulation results for each of percentage overshoot, rise time and settling time with comparison between two states (with PID controller and GA-PID). From simulation results, it is clear that the response of the system in the case of using PID controller is better than the case without controller by reducing the overshoot, rise time, and settling time. In addition, the response of system by using GA-PID is improved more than the previous two cases, and the system reached to optimization through reduce overshoot to zero and rise time, settling time lowest possible values, thus achieving the best results, led to improve, develop the operation, and performance of the BLDC motor.

Table 2. Control parameters

Parameters	With PID controller	With GA-PID
Kp	0.062988	0.183
Kd	4.7342e-5	4.995
Ki	3.2421	0.001

Table 3. Response of system

Parameters	With PID controller	With GA-PID
Overshoot	7.1%	0
Rise time	0.0279 sec	0.22×10 ⁻⁷ sec
Settling time	0.102 sec	0.65×10 ⁻⁷ sec

5. CONCLUSION

In the study, the genetic method was proposed to adjust the control parameters of the traditional PID controller that is designed as a BLDC motor control system, where the genetic controller has much higher time response characteristics comparative with the PID controller also it provides us with the initial point for the values of the control parameters. The GA-PID is the best in relations (settling time, rise time, and overshoot). In addition, the error associated with GA-PID is much less than the traditional control methods, therefore; GA-PID has succeeded in obtaining the best results for BLDC motor.

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